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Internship Report

Adaptation to local climate change with afforestation : a surface-atmospheric coupling approach at fine scale with regional climatic modelisation.

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Abstract

Afforestation has been mentioned in the IPCC and the Paris Agreement as a consequent solution to climate change mainly through mitigation, and sometimes adaptation. Forests are a sink of carbon and allow to take out carbon from the atmosphere, and cool the atmosphere at a global scale (mitigation). Then, forests can locally cool the surface through biophysic processes as evaporation, and create their own clouds and precipitations with destabilization of the atmosphere. This is why they can be used for local adaptation strategies. The IPCC reveals the potential of greening urban areas to adapt cities to climate change. However forests can also heat the surface through their low capacity to reflect the incoming solar radiation. Local afforestation can have different and complex answers on the surrounding climate according to the type of trees, the season and the region [IPCC Special Report Climate Change and Land]. It is then important to assess local afforestation adaptation strategies. A lot of studies assessed the biophysical effects of forest on regional climate, however, they looked at large scale afforestations, with 50km resolution. Studies of very local afforestation to assess local adaptation strategies are missing.

This study experiment an idealized local afforestation of the Gers department in France. Different simulations are run ; a reference historical one, a reference future one in a future climate of 2°C mean global warming level. Then afforestation simulations are made, by changing the vegetation cover of the surface, and run in the future climate. The effects of the local afforestation of the Gers are compared to the effect of global warming alone on this area.

This study assess a first tool coupling atmosphere and surface in a future climate at fine scale, with local afforestation experiences on the domain studied. The answers of climatic variables on the Gers to the local afforestation have similar scales than their answers to climate change. Local afforestation has strong effects on the Gers. Afforestation increase the local temperature of the Gers department, except in summer, where it cools the extremes. Afforestation enhance precipitation in winter thanks to dynamics, and enhance runoff in spring and summer thanks to the transpiration cycle of forests. The answers of climatic variables are complex to understand as they depend on the season, the variable, and the type of tree.

Then, simulations with afforestation of France, and of Europe and North Africa are run in the same period. It enables to study the impact of the afforestation scale on the answers of the Gers climatic variables. The key role of dynamics in afforestation experiments, which is dependant on the afforestation scale, is highlighted. The answers of climatic variables on the Gers can be opposed wether they answer to a local or to a large scale afforestation. To assess local politic adaptation to climate change via afforestation, local scale afforestation experiments may be better to run because of the dynamics. Large scale afforestation with small resolution would highlight local and one dimensional answers to afforestation, but not the dynamics induced by local afforestation.

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1 Introduction

In the Earth System, forests are part of the biosphere, on the land. Many other components take part of this system, such as the hydrosphere and the atmosphere, and they all interact and function together. The land hosts many processes and feedbacks, driven by the sun, and those processes impact the atmosphere and therefore, the climate. Those processes can be biogeochemical (cycle of carbon, cycle of nitrogen) or biophysical (energy cycle, water cycle), as explained in the Special Report of the IPCC Climate Change and Land, [15], 2019.

Humans can modify the land to use it, and this is called land use change or land cover change. The main land cover change is the expansion of agriculture which often induce deforestation. Land use change alters the properties of the surface, and changes the processes between the land and the atmosphere. It impacts the atmosphere and therefore the climate ([15]).

Historical changes in anthropogenic land cover change have induced a mean annual global warming of the air with biogeochemical effects, mostly through deforestation and carbon emissive land uses, which enhance green house gases. They have also induced a cooling from biophysical effects, mainly because the global anthropogenic land use change has increased the global land surface albedo. The land has reflected more incoming solar energy, and it has decreased the radiative forcing of the surface by $-0.15\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, inducing a cooling ([15]).

In average, historical land use changes have induced a mean global annual warming of $+0.078^\circ\text{C}$. This small warming is due to the competition between the biochemical warming and the biophysical cooling, and the biogeochemical effect dominate. Then at the regional scale, the biophysical effects are stronger and can dampen or exacerbate the biogeochemical warming. The sign of those effects at the regional scale depends on the season, the region, and the soil moisture ([15]).

The impacts of the future land cover changes on climate along the scenario RCP 8.5 are estimated with a $+0.2^\circ\text{C}$ chemical warming and a -0.1°C physical cooling, at the globe level. At the regional scale, future anthropogenic land cover change will have a significant effect on temperature via biophysical effects. There is a lack of knowledge on if it will dampen or enhance the chemical warming across the regions ([15]).

Afforestation is one kind of land use change. It is the act of growing forests where there were no trees before. Reforestation is the act of growing more trees where there are already trees. In this study, we will talk of afforestation for both terms.

Afforestation is a lot considered as a mitigation strategy for the climate at a global scale. Indeed, forests absorb a lot of carbon dioxide, and they store carbon. By taking out carbon from the atmosphere, they reduce the green house gases, and cool the mean temperature at the scale of the globe. The IPCC reveals the potential from options in agroforestry, forestry, and landscape diversification that could be upscaled in the near term into most regions, and could have from immediate profitable impacts to profitable impacts in three to ten years ([5]). Then, the Paris Agreements expect forestation to contribute about a quarter of mitigation efforts for attacking global warming. Afforestation is also looked as an adaptation strategy to climate change, but it is very less developed. Urban green infrastructures have an important role in adapting cities to climate change, for instance to reduce the air temperature, which can help improve human health and comfort ([15]). The local scale is also an interesting scale to adopt adaptation strategy to climate change as it is a small scale, with less policy makers who have to agree on a decision. With climate change, cities, departments, regions may consider adaptation strategy a their small scale, to adapt locally.

At the local scale, afforestation impact the regional climate through biochemical and biogeophysical

processes at the surface. Biophysical effects are stronger at the regional scale than at the globe scale ([15]). Then, biophysical impacts can be comparable to the green house gases variations impacts on temperature response at a regional scale, which highlights their importance ([4]). It is important to study them when afforestation is considered.

In this figure 1, adapted from [17], are illustrated the biogeophysical effects of afforestation. Among

Figure 1: Biogeophysical processes with afforestation

them there is the impact of forest on short wave radiation. The very low albedo of forests tends to decrease the albedo of the surface with afforestation, which decreases the shortwave radiation reflected to the atmosphere and therefore, increases the net shortwave radiation absorption by the earth surface, finally leading to an increase in the temperature.

This heating albedo effect is opposed to the cooling effect of turbulent flux induced by forests ([4],[7],[3]).

The forest roughness transfers the excess of radiative energy at the surface to the atmosphere via turbulent heat fluxes ([3]), and forests evaporate a lot. They have deep roots to pump water, a high transpiration and a quick evaporation of rain on their canopy. This leads to a cooling of the surface. Afforestation and surface heterogeneity can also impact circulation patterns. Forests can generate their own clouds and precipitations with convection, especially in summer. ([17],[14]).

Forest can also generate its own circulation pattern, or breeze. Finally, forests tend to decrease stream flows ([17],[5]).

Biophysical effects of afforestation are complex, not fully understood, and they depend on the latitude, the season, the snow regime of the area, the soil moisture, and the type of tree.

To our knowledge, most studies have looked at afforestation impacts at large continental scale (e.g. Amazonia, Europe, North America) and using relatively low-resolution climate models. For example, the project LUCAS (Land Use Across Scales) ([7]), work on the robust biophysical effects of an idealized afforestation over Europe. This study has been reproduced in North America to study the robust biophysical effects of an idealized afforestation over North America ([1]). They try to understand and measure how sensitive the climate is to very large changes. The effects of a local afforestation, at a small scale where decision are easier to make, isn't really studied yet. However those policies may interest more and more municipalities or countries in the next few years with

climate change, and raise several scientific questions and preoccupations. Biophysical effects can be really strong on regional scales, and the impacts of biophysical effects from a local afforestation on the surrounding climate aren't really studied. We don't really know how sensitive climate is to a very local change.

The IPCC also observe a lack in literature on "an estimate of the impacts that natural disturbances in forests will have on local climates". And "there is not enough litterature yet that compares both biophysical and biogeochemical effects of realistic scenarios of foreststation" ([15]).

Those informations could be key in the near future. If a department want to adapt to climate change locally, would it be useful to forest such a small area ? Would it have effects on the local temperature and water cycle, or would it be negligible ?

Studies of local afforestation could also be interesting as small spatial scales can impact large scales, and extreme events can regionally amplify one another ([5]). Furthermore it can be difficult to separate local and non local effects without separating experiments ([3]).

This is why the focus is put in this study on evaluation methods and options to assess local adaptation strategy policies with afforestation.

To our knowledge, those questions have been less studied so far due to both a general focus on mitigation issues in climate change studies and therefore on large scales and to the lack of adapted climate modelling tools. Indeed, adresssing the local climate impacts of afforestation or reforestation requires at least high-resolution climate models with a complex representation of the land surfaces, an interactive atmosphere-land coupling and a capacity to handle land-use-land-cover change scenarios. These tools are currently only in their infancy ([7],[4]).

Therefore, the goal of this study is to perform local afforestation experiments, to study the effects of a local afforestation on the surrounding climate.

For the study, we will afforest the Gers department in France, and analyze the impact of the department's afforestation on the water cycle and the climate at a local scale in the future, in comparison to global warming effects alone in the same future period.

In addition, this study will also assess which afforestation scale has the most impacts on the local variable answers. To do so, afforestation simulations of France, and of Europe and North Africa will be done, and we will study their effects inside the Gers borders.

We will now look at the methods used to lead our work (2), then we will assess the results of Gers afforestation on seasonal water availability and regional climate. We will also look at the afforestation scale impact, and finally discuss (4) and conclude (5) on our work.

2 Methods

2.1 Main principles

The principle of the study is to compare the effect of climate change to the effects of regional afforestation. To do so, one historical reference simulation and one future reference simulation are run. The difference between both gives the effects of global warming. Then, future simulations with a modified vegetation cover are run. The modification of vegetation is the afforestation. The difference between the future simulation with afforestation and the future reference simulation gives the effect of regional afforestation.

The simulation with afforestation of the Gers enables to study the variation of Gers climatic variables

in response to the Gers afforestation. Comparing those variations to the ones in response to climate change enables to see if the local afforestation of the Gers has enhanced or dampened the effect of climate change.

Then, future simulations with afforestation of France, and of Europe and North Africa, allow to study if the answer of the Gers climatic variables depend on the afforestation scale, and how. It makes a total of 5 simulations (explained in part 2.3).

2.2 Models

The study is conducted using the version 6.4 of the regional model Aire Limitée Adaptation dynamique Développement International (ALADIN), called CNRM-ALADIN64 ([13],[9]).

It is based on a bi-spectral, semi-implicit and semi-Lagrangian advection scheme, has 91 vertical levels and is used with a resolution of 12km.

It is a Regional Climate Model (RCM) forced at its boundaries (lateral and surface) by large-scale datasets coming from global reanalyses or global climate models (GCM).

ALADIN uses the version 8 of the surface modeling platform named SURFEX (SURface EXternalisée) ([8]). In this platform, the model ISBA treats the interaction between the surface, the biosphere and the atmosphere (ISBA stands for Interaction Surface Biosphere Atmosphere). It has an interactive vegetation scheme that includes, in particular, an evolving LAI and the representation of the anti-transpiration effect and the CO2 fertilization effect.

For each grid cell, ISBA models four tiles : lakes, sea, towns, and nature. For each tile, ISBA computes an energy and a water budget, and the final budget of the grid cell is computed from the four resulting tile budgets ([11]). Then, the nature tile is separated in 12 different patches, for 12 vegetation types, which come from 19 plant functional types (pfts) from the ECOCLIMAP database ([12]). Each SURFEX patch has its own humidity vertical profil, energy and water budget. The energy and water budget of the tile nature is computed from the 12 budgets of the 12 patches.

In the 12 SURFEX vegetation patches, three are used for trees ; tropical trees, evergreens trees, and broadleaves trees. In the Gers department, only evergreens and broadleaves are present.

SURFEX is coupled to CTRIP ([8]), the routing river model of the CNRM (CNRM version of Total Runoff Integrated Pathways), thanks to the OASIS Model Coupling Toolkit (OASIS-MCT) coupler ([6]). CTRIP converts the runoff simulated by SURFEX into drainage going into aquifers, and into river discharges, which then go to oceans to close the water budget.

ALADIN has a fully interactive aerosol scheme named TACTIC ([13]). It includes various anthropogenic and natural aerosol types that are emitted, transported, deposited and interact with the radiation scheme and the cloud scheme.

The regional climate model will take into account the biophysical effects of the afforestation experiment made in SURFEX. It will not take into account the biochemical affect of the afforestation experiment. To take into account the biochemical effect of afforestation, an afforestation experiment on a global climate model should be run.

2.3 Simulation setup

All the simulations are forced by the Earth System Model of the CNRM (French National Center of Meteorological Research) ESM-CNRM-2-1, with the Global Climate Model ARPEGE-IFS ([16]). The domain used is the same as in previous EURO-CORDEX simulations performed with models CNRM-ALADIN53 and CNRM-ALADIN63 ([2],[18]). The resolution is 12km.

5 simulations are made in the study. Two reference simulations are made, one driven by a CMIP6

acronyme	modèle	modèle forceur	domaine	GWL	résolution	scénario	dates	forçage afforestation
his_reference	Aladin64	CNRM-ESM2-1	Eurocordex	0.48°C	12km	/	1986-2005	/
ssp_reference	Aladin64	CNRM-ESM2-1	Eurocordex	2°C	12km	SSP3-7.0	2043-2062	/
ssp_gerforest	Aladin64	CNRM-ESM2-1	Eurocordex	2°C	12km	SSP3-7.0	2043-2062	sur Gers
ssp_fraforest	Aladin64	CNRM-ESM2-1	Eurocordex	2°C	12km	SSP3-7.0	2043-2062	sur France
ssp_eurforest	Aladin64	CNRM-ESM2-1	Eurocordex	2°C	12km	SSP3-7.0	2043-2062	sur EURO-CORDEX

Figure 2: The 5 simulations run in the study. In khaki, the historical reference simulation his_reference. In orange red, the future reference simulation ssp_reference. In light blue, the future simulation with Gers afforestation ssp_gerforest. In light green, the future simulation with France afforestation ssp_fraforest. In dark green, the future simulation with EURO-CORDEX simulation ssp_eurforest.

historical CNRM-ESM2-1 simulation, and one driven by a future scenario (SSP3-7.0, Shared Socio-economic Pathways) with CNRM-ESM2-1. Both are run across 20 years, with 10 years of spin up (explained in part 2.4).

The historical simulation is run on the period 1986-2005, a reference period commonly used in the last IPCC report ([5]). It is a period with a mean global warming level of +0.5°C in CNRM-ESM2 above pre-industrial levels in the driving GCM CNRM-ESM2-1 r1i1p1f2 run. It is called his_reference (figure 2).

The future simulation is run on a period with a mean global warming level of +2°C above preindustrial levels (GWL2) in CNRM-ESM2. According to the forcing simulation CNRM-ESM2-1 r1i1p1f2, the corresponding period on the chosen scenario is 2043-2063. It is called ssp_reference (figure 2). It is worth to note that the SSP3-7.0 scenario is the chosen scenario by the French minister to assess the National Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change. Then, it is the objectif of the Paris agreements to limit global warming under 2°C. For the scenario SSP3-7.0, the 2°C global warming set by the Paris agreements is reached at the middle of the century.

The impacts of climate change alone are characterized by the difference between ssp_reference and his_reference.

Then, simulations with changes in vegetation cover are made to evaluate the effect of afforestation in comparison to climate change effect.

The main afforestation simulation is the one with the afforestation of the Gers department (in France), called ssp_gerforest (figure 2).

A department was chosen as it is an interesting scale where decisions can be made by policy makers. Another area in EURO-CORDEX domain than Gers could have been studied, and could give different results. The obtained results won't be generalized to every department of France or Europe.

However the Gers is chosen thanks to its large size, its localization (not in the sea side or in the mountains), and its little forest density. It enables a large increase of forested areas in the idealized afforestation experiment. The Gers is highly impacted by climate change on its hydrological resources, and there is still water positive perspectives that may happen with adaptation. It is an interesting practical case.

The difference between `ssp_gerforest` and `ssp_reference` allows to characterize the effects of a local-scale afforestation strategy in a climate change context.

Two other afforestation simulations are made, one afforestation of France only called `ssp_fraforest`, and one afforestation of the EURO-CORDEX domain called `ssp_eurforest` (figure 2). These simulations are useful to study the impact of the afforestation scale on the Gers temperature and hydrological responses. The difference inside the Gers borders between `ssp_fraforest` and `ssp_reference` shows the effects of France afforestation on the Gers climatic variables. The difference inside the Gers borders between `ssp_eurforest` and `ssp_reference` shows the effects of EURO-CORDEX afforestation on the Gers climatic variables.

Comparing the results of the three afforestation scales impacts on Gers climatic variables allows to tell the role of afforestation scale on local responses of climatic variables.

2.4 Spin up strategy

A double spin up of 10 years is used before running the afforestation simulations (figure 3). This strategy is assessed by looking at the Soil Wetness Index (SWI). It represents the water in the ground usable by the vegetation.

In the figure 4 (a), no drifts are observed during the 20 years simulation for the variable SWI of `ssp_gerforest` simulation. In the figure 4 (b), the SWI is well conserved from the first 5 years spin up to the second 5 years spin with vegetation cover change. There is no drop between both curves. It means that no water is “added” to the model, the SWI is well conserved with the afforestation. The spinup strategy is working, with no choc between the runs, and an equilibrium reached for each run.

2.5 Afforestation Method

The afforestation method of the LUCAS project (Land Use Across Scales) is used ([7]). This research project does idealized afforestation experiments over Europe to study the biophysical impacts of afforestation at regional scale. The total density of trees is increased to 100% where trees can potentially grow, and the initial proportion of different tree types is conserved. Trees are supposed to potentially grow everywhere, except on areas of permanent snow or ice, bare soil and rocks areas. If no trees are present in the grid cell, but can potentially grow (i.e. the grid cell is not covered only by permanent snow or ice, bare soil or rocks), the dominant tree in the latitude band of the grid cell is implemented. In practice, the Nature tile of each grid cell in SURFEX is modified. Among the 12 vegetation patches, the patches for rocks, permanent snow and ice and bare soil are not modified, and the patches for evergreens and broadleaves are maximized, by keeping the initial proportion of each tree in the cell.

This afforestation method is drastic, and academic, in order to study the robust biophysic effects of forests. This afforestation method doesn’t aim to be realistic, but to maximise the effect of forest

Figure 3: The pink curve is the spin up for `ssp_reference`. It aims for an equilibrium for each climatic variable of the regional model ALADIN, after the forcing simulation CNRM-ESM2-1 r1i1p1f2. The black curve is the run of the simulation `ssp_reference`. The pink curve is also the first part of the spin up for afforestation simulation. The vegetation cover change is introduced at the end of this first spin up. The green curve is the second part of the spin up. It aims for an equilibrium for each surface climatic variable of ALADIN, after the afforestation cover change. Each vegetation patch on SURFEX has an humidity vertical profile, and replacing a crop patch by a tree patch is a choc for the soil, so the ground variables (as humidity) need to adapt and reach an equilibrium. The blue curve is the run for afforestation simulations (`ssp_gerforest`, `ssp_fraforest`, `ssp_eurforest`).

to learn on them. As a consequence, this scientific choice has its limits, as it is not likely to give result we could observe in reality, because the afforestation is idealized. However it is interesting as the result can approach effects we could observe.

Today, there are mostly agricultural crops on the Gers. With the idealized afforestation of the Gers in the model, 68% of total forest density was added, with 37% of broadleaves added and 31% of evergreens added (figure 5 and 6). Those results are computed with the sum of total forest density (%) of each tile Nature in each grid cell of the Gers, before and after afforestation. Spatially, broadleaves trees are added mostly in the middle of the Gers, and evergreens on the west side of the Gers (figure 6).

The dominant vegetation in the Gers after afforestation is broadleaves trees (figure 8 (b)). The dominant vegetation type on each grid for the four simulations can be seen in Figure 7, zoomed on EURO-CORDEX domain, and in the figure 8, zoomed on the Gers department.

Figure 4: Soil Wetness Index. Same explanation as figure 3. The spin up with the vegetation cover change (green curve) is the one for the Gers afforestation only. The afforestation simulation run (blue curve) is `ssp_gerforest`.

(%)	Feuillus	Conifères	C3	C4	Irrigated crops	Grass	Irrigated grass	Bare soil	Rocks	Total
Avant afforestation du Gers	13	4	37	5	5	21	0	13	2	100
Après afforestation du Gers	50	35	0	0	0	0	0	13	2	100

Figure 5: Vegetation patches of SURFEX on the Gers department, before afforestation of the Gers (`ssp_reference`) and after afforestation of the Gers (`ssp_gerforest`). C3 and C4 are two kinds of crops with different photosynthesis, photorespiration and growth. Examples of C3 crops are cereals, oats, rice and wheat (most plants are C3). Examples of C4 crops are corn and sugercan (C4 are rarer).

3 Results

The changes in temperature answers, and the changes in water resources variables, in response of climate change with afforestation, are assessed and explained in this section.

3.1 Seasonal cycle

The seasonality of vegetation is strong and important when studying the impact of forests on climate ([3]).

Figures 9 and 10 show different behaviours for `ssp_gerforest` and `ssp_reference` simulations according to the season, with the leaf area index and the transpiration. In the reference simulations, there are 83% of non-tree soils in the model (figure 5). Non-tree soils stands for the combination of C3 crops, C4 crops, irrigated crops, grass, bare soil and rocks (figure 5). In the `ssp_gerforest` simulation, there are 85% of trees (figure 5).

In autumn (SON) and winter (DJF), trees leaf area index is higher than the non-tree soils ones and still they transpire less (figure 10) ; those seasons correspond to the slowing of the vegetative cycle for forests. Broadleaves lost their leaves and evergreens are less active even if they keep their

Figure 6: Difference for each grid cell of the Gers department, in the tile nature, between the density of broadleaves trees or evergreen trees after and before afforestation. The greener the grid cell, the higher the tree density that is added after afforestation.

Figure 7: Dominant vegetation type within 12 SURFEX patches on each grid cell. Current repartition of vegetation in SURFEX.

Figure 8: Same as figure 7, zoomed on the Gers department

spines.

In spring (MAM), we observe the same leaf area index for non-tree soils and trees (figure 9). In the

Figure 9: Leaf Area Index. Historical reference simulation in brown : his_reference, future reference SSP 3-7.0 simulation in red : ssp_reference, future SSP 3-7.0 simulation with Gers afforestation in Green : ssp_gerforest. The mean across the 20 years of simulation on the Gers department are computed for each month. Months with significant differences (at 95% confidence level) between afforested and future reference simulations are shown with a bold green dot. Months with significant differences (at 95% confidence level) between future reference and historical reference simulations are shown with a bold red dot.

Figure 10: Vegetation transpiration. Same as Figure 9.

surface model used, at equivalent LAI, trees transpire less than non-tree soils because they have a better resistance to evaporation ([10]).

Then, in summer (JJA), LAI becomes really higher for trees, it is the period where they are the most active, with a strong photosynthesis. As a consequence in summer, transpiration is higher in ssp_gerforest.

This effect goes down with the arrival of the autumn and the decreasing of the insolation.

Seasonal effects of regional afforestation on the Gers climatic variables will be studied. The regular

Figure 12: Same as figure 11

The change in the precipitation response to climate change with afforestation is much more difficult to explain as it is not directly related to 1D radiative effect. In winter is observed a general circulation with a westerly general wind on the west coast of France, and on the Gers (Figure 13).

Figure 13: General circulation in the future reference simulation $ssp_{reference}$. Mean of every winter months of the simulation time, 2043-2062.

With afforestation, the horizontal 10m wind on the Gers is decreased (Figure 14 (a)). Forests are an obstacle for the coming horizontal wind. With afforestation, ascendances at 850 hPa increase at the entrance of the Gers (west side) (Figure 14(b)), and subsidences at 850 hPa increase at the end of the Gers (east side). The forest reduces the incoming westerly wind with the increase of the surface friction, as they increase surface rugosity. It creates convergences of horizontal wind at the edge of the forest on the west side of the Gers, and result in this strong ascendance. The

Figure 14: Same as figure 11

westerly wind coming from the ocean is moistened. Its ascendance with afforestation creates the precipitation surplus compared to global warming effect alone. An interesting loop is observed, with ascendancy on the west and subsidency on the east of the Gers (figure 14(b)), and precipitations fall in the middle (figure 11(b)).

With afforestation, a part of the precipitation surplus observed is convective precipitation (not shown), which support the hypothesis of dynamically-enhanced precipitation.

Furthermore, with afforestation the relative humidity decreases on the Gers (Figure 15). The low atmosphere is warmer thanks to the radiative processes explained. The water holding capacity of the atmosphere increases, so the relative humidity decreases. With a lower relative humidity, precipitation should be less frequent. The change in relative humidity with afforestation can't explain the precipitation anomaly. Only the dynamic aspect does. With afforestation, the evaporation

Figure 15: Surface relative humidity. Same as figure 11.

Figure 16: Water budget on the Gers department, winter mean (DJF). From left to right, there are the precipitations, the evaporation, the run off, and the tendency of moisture in the ground (called 'bilan' on the figure). In brown are the variables for the historical reference simulation (1986-2005) $his_{reference}$. In red is the future reference simulation (2043-2062) $ssp_{reference}$. In green is the future simulation with Gers afforestation $ssp_{gerforest}$ (2043-2062). The mean of the variables on the Gers and on every december months (december january february) of the 20 years simulation is computed. The circle upon red bars mean the difference between $ssp_{reference}$ and $his_{reference}$ is significant on the Gers. The star upon green bars mean the difference between $ssp_{gerforest}$ and $ssp_{reference}$ is significant on the Gers.

answer to climate change at the surface switch of sign, and decreases. Horizontal 10m wind decreases too (Figure 14(a)), and horizontal wind enhances evaporation. In winter in our model, trees also have a higher resistance to evaporation than crops, grass and bare soil, which explains a lower surface evaporation with afforestation.

With afforestation the runoff decreases significantly less. As the precipitation decreases less and the evaporation decreases, there is more water to runoff with afforestation in winter (Figure 16). Soil moisture answer to climate change is reversed with afforestation and increases significantly (Figure 16). It also answers to the higher precipitations and lower evaporation with afforestation compared to climate change alone.

The variables responses to afforestation are homogeneous inside the Gers department. Only the precipitations have an interesting spatial structure, as they fall in the middle of the Gers between the ascendancy and the subsidence, as explained.

3.3 Spring : MAM

In this section, the effect of Gers afforestation is compared to global warming effect on the Gers climatic variables, in spring. In spring, with global warming, the 2m temperature increases by $+0.9^{\circ}\text{C}$. Precipitations decrease by -0.2 mm/day and the runoff decreases by -0.2 mm/day. ((34)) With the Gers afforestation, the 2m temperature increases by $+0.7^{\circ}\text{C}$ more (Figure 17(a), which worsens the effect of climate change alone. Then, the runoff decreases less with a difference of $+0.1$ mm/day (Figure 17(b)) (34).

Figure 17: Difference between $ssp_{gerforest}$ and $ssp_{reference}$, meaned on every spring months for the 20 years of simulation. It is the anomaly if we afforest the Gers department in the climate change context of the period 2043-2062, in mean on spring. The hatched parts mean the difference between $ssp_{gerforest}$ and $ssp_{reference}$ is not significant at a level of 95%.

With afforestation, the albedo increases in spring, without big differences from winter (not shown). The short wave upward radiation decreases, and the decrease is stronger in spring than in winter (figure 18). The insolation is stronger in spring than in winter (not shown). At similar albedo but with higher insolation, the upward shortwave radiation at surface decreases more (Figure 18). There is more energy surplus at the surface in spring and it results in a stronger warming ; $+0.7^{\circ}\text{C}$ in spring compared to $+0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ in winter (34).

The evaporation answer to climate change has an opposed sign with afforestation. A strong significant decrease in evaporation is observed with afforestation (Figure 19).

With afforestation, the precipitations answer remain stable (figure 19). Then, the run off decreases significantly less, and it is explained by the precipitation stability plus the significant decrease in evaporation (Figure 19). The soil moisture answer with afforestation is opposed to the one with climate change alone. An increase in soil moisture is observed. It is also explain by the strong decrease in evaporation (Figure 19).

With afforestation, a strong drop of transpiration at the surface is observed, and it is an opposed answer to the one to climate change alone (Figure 20(a)). The drop in transpiration highly explains the drop of evaporation with afforestation.

Figure 18: Short Wave up going radiation at the surface. Same as figure 17.

Figure 19: Water budget on the Gers department, spring mean (MAM). As Figure 16 with spring.

With afforestation, the leaf area index (LAI) of the surface doesn't significantly change compared to climate change effect alone (Figure 20(b)), with crops, grass and bare soil at the surface.

Spring is the time of year where trees grow up again and their leaves aren't totally developed. It explains how the reference surface with grass, crops and bare soil mainly can have the same LAI

Figure 20: Difference between $ssp_{gerforest}$ and $ssp_{reference}$, spring mean. In red is the future reference simulation (2043-2062) $ssp_{reference}$. In green is the future simulation with Gers afforestation $ssp_{gerforest}$ (2043-2062). The mean of the variables on the Gers and on every spring (march april may) months of the 20 years simulation is computed. The star upon the green bar mean the difference between $ssp_{gerforest}$ and $ssp_{reference}$ is significant on the Gers.

as the afforested soil with trees mainly. Then, in SURFEX, at an equivalent leaf area index, trees are more resistant to evaporation than grass, crops and bare soil ([10]). It explains the drop of transpiration in spring with afforestation.

The horizontal 10 m wind decreases with afforestation as forests act as an obstacle (Figure 21). As horizontal wind enhances evaporation, the slowing of the wind could also explain a part of the

Figure 21: 10m horizontal wind. Same as figure x.

transpiration drop with afforestation.

The only spatial structure observed in spring is for the runoff, and is very little. The runoff surplus with afforestation isn't on the west of the Gers, where mostly evergreens are added. The transpiration drop resulting in a higher runoff may be more specific to broadleaves than to evergreens. The other variables responses to afforestation are homogeneous inside the Gers department.

3.4 Summer : JJA

In this section, the effect of Gers afforestation is compared to global warming effect on the Gers climatic variables, in summer. In summer, with global warming, the 2m temperature increases by +1.7 °C in the Gers department. Precipitation decreases by -0.25 mm/day, and runoff decreases by -0.04 mm/day (34). With the afforestation of the Gers, the runoff decreases less than with climate change alone, with a difference of +0.03 mm/day, which compensates to a large extent the impact of global warming alone (Figure 22) (34). The albedo induced upward shortwave radiation decrease,

Figure 22: Water budget on the Gers department, summer mean (JJA). As Figure 16 with summer.

leading to the surface heating, is still occurring in summer (not shown). A strong increase in transpiration, and so in evaporation is observed (Figure 23(a)). This strong decrease of evaporation induces a cooling of the surface.

There is a competition between the warming induced by the decrease in albedo and the cooling induced by the increase in evaporation. In the end, the warming induced by afforestation isn't significant.

With afforestation, we observe a leaf area index really stronger on the Gers (Figure 23(b)), and a soil wetness index really higher (Figure 23(c)).

Summer is the season with the stronger insolation of the year (not shown). Trees develop their leaves at their maximum and have a strong photosynthesis. The leaf area index of the afforested soil becomes stronger than the leaf area index of the reference soil (crops, grass, and bare soil mainly). With higher leaf area index, the trees transpire more, and there is more total evaporation at the surface (figure 23(a)). Then, trees roots depth are deeper than the roots of crops or grass [citer

Figure 23: Difference between $ssp_{gerforest}$ and $ssp_{reference}$, meaned on every summer months for the 20 years of simulation. It is the anomaly if we afforest the Gers department in the climate change context of the period 2043-2062, in mean on summer. The hatched parts mean the difference between $ssp_{gerforest}$ and $ssp_{reference}$ is not significant at a level of 95%.

surfaces]. Trees roots can reach higher moisture areas in the deep soil. The soil wetness index is computed on this roots depth. It increases when there are more trees. It contributes to the higher trees transpiration, and the higher surface evaporation with afforestation (figure 24).

Furthermore, trees big leaves can intercept rain and evaporate it quickly rather than giving it to the ground. With afforestation, precipitations fall on the canopy and on the ground, rather than falling mainly on the ground. The quick evaporation on the canopy can also explain the higher evaporation on the ground and at the canopy observed with afforestation in Figure 24. The higher

Figure 24: Evaporation budget. From left to right, there are the evaporation, the transpiration, and the difference between evaporation and transpiration, which is considered in the study as the evaporation on the ground and on the canopy (called 'evap cano solnu' on the figure). Transpiration is a part of evaporation, so the evaporation is equal to the two other terms. Same as figure 22.

leaf area index and the higher soil wetness index with afforestation can explain the higher transpiration and evaporation at the surface which is observed.

An interesting spatial structure is observed for the LAI and the latent heat flux (figure 23(a) and (b)). They are stronger in the center of the Gers, where broadleaves trees are added (figure 6), and weaker in the west side of the Gers, where evergreens are added (figure 6). Broadleaves have larger leaves than evergreens which have spines. Broadleaves transpire more than evergreens, inducing a higher evaporation (correlation of 0.46 between broadleaves and latent heat flux, and of 0.07 for the same correlation with evergreen trees) (figure 27(a)).

It results in a spatial correlation for the temperature increase. In summer, temperature doesn't change with afforestation in mean on the Gers, but it increases lightly on the west were evergreens are added (figure 25). Less transpiration happens there, so there is less cooling to compensate the albedo induced warming.

This spatial structure depending on the type of trees is even more observed when studying the

Figure 25: 2m temperature. Same as figure 23.

temperature extremes. Temperature extremes decrease where broadleaves are added, and remain stable where evergreens are added (figure 26).

Broadleaves trees give away most of their energy via evapotranspiration (figure 27(a)), leading to a cooling of temperature extremes in the Gers (figure 26). Evergreens trees give away most of their energy via sensible heat flux rather than with evapotranspiration (fig 27(b)). No cooling of extreme temperature is observed above evergreen trees (figure 26), and a warming of the regular temperature is observed (fig 25).

Lastly, an increase in precipitation is observed, and mostly above broadleaves. It is an interesting spatial structure as broadleaves transpire more than evergreens. However it is not significant.(figure 28(a))

It is the only explanation for the significant increase in runoff (the evaporation increase cannot explain a decrease in runoff) (figure 28(b)). The strong evapotranspiration surplus with afforestation, plus the cooling of the atmosphere via the same evapotranspiration, could lead to a saturation of the atmosphere, specifically above broadleaves which transpire more than evergreens. It is a local water recycling of evaporation through precipitations. Depending on the way precipitation

Figure 26: Maximum of the daily temperature maxima, for each summer on the 20 years of simulation. Same as figure 23.

Figure 27: Spatial scatter plot of the heat flux (ordinate axis) according to the type of forest density (abscissa). The type of forest can be broadleaf (light green), evergreen (dark green), or total forest density ; broadleaf + evergreen (black). There are 39 dots by color, for the 39 grid cells inside the Gers department. For each grid cell, there is a value of heat flux on this cell, a value of broadleaf density on this cell, and a value of evergreen density on this cell. The regression curve and the correlation coefficient between the heat flux and the type of tree are in the corresponding color.

are falling, they could happen and the ttest consider them not significant, for instance if they are strong, but spread in time.

The spatial structure of the runoff isn't explained.

The soil moisture significantly decreases, because the surface evaporation significantly increase (fig 22).

Figure 28: Same as figure 23.

3.5 Afforestation scale impact on the Gers answers to afforestation

In this section, the effect of the afforestation scale on the Gers variable responses is assessed. Local or large scale afforestations may impact differently the climatic response of the Gers. It is worth noting that the European-scale afforestation experiment corresponds to the spirit of the CORDEX FPS-LUCAS protocol ([7]).

3.5.1 Comparison of afforestation simulations and reference simulation

The climatic variables responses on the Gers have similar magnitude orders across the three afforestation scales (figures 29 and 30). The effect of afforestation on the Gers isn't stronger for large scale afforestations. This is a first surprising result.

For the three afforestation scales in winter and in spring, the temperature is significantly higher in response to climate change with afforestation (fig 30).

In winter, evaporation significantly decreases, and soil moisture significantly increases for all afforestation simulations. In spring, evaporation significantly decreases, runoff increases, and soil moisture decreases significantly less for all afforestation simulations. In summer, evaporation significantly increases and soil moisture significantly decreases for all afforestation simulations (fig 29).

3.5.2 Comparison of large scale afforestation simulations and local afforestation simulation

A most surprising result is that the Gers climatic variables responses can be stronger and even opposed when only the Gers is afforested, in comparison with afforestation of France or of EURO-CORDEX domain. Local afforestation can reveal new physical processes, which can even dominate. This section assesses variables with significant differences in their responses whether the afforesta-

Figure 29: Water budget inside the Gers department. From left to right, precipitations, evaporation, runoff, and soil moisture (called 'bilan' on the figure) (mm/day). Color code: red for the future reference simulation $ssp_{reference}$ (2043-2062), dark green for the future simulation with EURO-CORDEX afforestation $ssp_{eurforest}$, light green for the future simulation with France afforestation $ssp_{fraforest}$ and light blue for the future simulation with the Gers afforestation $ssp_{gerforest}$. The stars upon the bars mean that the difference between the simulation and the $ssp_{reference}$ simulation is statistically significant on the Gers. The crosses upon the bars mean that the difference between the simulation and the $ssp_{gerforest}$ run is statistically significant on the Gers.

tion is local ($ssp_{gerforest}$) or widespread ($ssp_{fraforest}$, $ssp_{eurforest}$).

Evaporation - Accross winter spring and summer, the evaporation is significantly higher in response to a local afforestation than to a large scale afforestation (Figure 29). In winter and spring, it is because the evaporation response to climate change decreases less with the Gers afforestation. In summer, it is because the evaporation response to climate change with local afforestation is opposed to the one with large scale afforestation. It increases with the Gers afforestation while it slightly decreases for large scale afforestations.

10m horizontal wind - Accross winter, spring and summer, the 10m horizontal wind is significantly stronger in response to the Gers afforestation than to large scale afforestations (Figure 31). It is because the horizontal wind response to climate change decreases less with the local afforestation.

The surface horizontal wind decreases with forest density ([14]). Indeed, trees act as obstacles and slow the surface horizontal wind, by increasing the surface rugosity.

The slowdown of the wind on the Gers result of the local effect of afforestation, but also of the effect of trees before the Gers, slowing down the westerly wind coming into the Gers.

The horizontal wind is significantly stronger when only the Gers is afforested than with France or EURO-CORDEX afforestation, because there are less trees on the west of the Gers to stop the incoming westerly wind.

The horizontal wind enhances surface evaporation and tree transpiration. There is a high positive spatial correlation between wind and evaporation and transpiration (not shown). As a consequence, Gers evaporation is significantly higher with local afforestation than with widespread afforestation.

Figure 30: 2m temperature. Same color code as figure 29

Figure 31: 10m horizontal wind. Same color code as figure 29.

2m temperature - Accross winter, spring and summer, the temperature is significantly lower in response to local afforestation than to large scale afforestations (figure 30). In winter and spring, it is because the temperature response to climate change decreases less with local afforestation. In summer, it is because the temperature response to climate change remains stable with the Gers afforestation while it increases with large scale afforestations.

Those changes of temperature in response to the afforestation scale are correlated and can be explained by the changes of evaporation in response to the afforestation scale. An increase in evaporation induce a cooling of the near surface air temperature, and a decrease in evaporation induce a warming.

Precipitations - In winter, it is interesting to notice that with the Gers afforestation, ascendancies are on the west side of the Gers (Figure 32(a)). As explained in section 3.2 it induces a precipitation surplus all over the department. However with France and EURO-CORDEX afforestation, ascendancies are more located on the west coast of France (Figures 32(a) and (b)), and the precipitation

excess falls near the coast (not shown). There are no precipitations surplus on the Gers. Dynamics changes with the afforestation scale, and so the precipitation answer to afforestation. Although the precipitation answers aren't significantly different between local and large scale afforestations, the dynamic effect is still interesting to notice.

Figure 32: Pressure tendency at 850 hPa. Same as Figure 11.

In spring, precipitations are significantly higher in response to the Gers afforestation than in response to large scale afforestations. It is because precipitations response to climate change remains stable with local afforestation, while it decreases with large scale afforestations.

The temperature increase in response to climate change is higher with large scale afforestations (figure 30(b)), so its water holding capacity increases in those cases. This result in a decrease of precipitations in answer to climate change with large scale afforestations.

With local scale afforestation, temperature response to climate change also increases (figure 30(b)), so precipitations could also decrease. However, the evaporation response to climate change decreases less, so the atmosphere is more moistened than for large scale afforestation (figure 29(b)). The atmosphere can better lead to precipitations. Then the sensible heat flux increase in response to climate change is very located, compared to the response to large scale afforestation (figure 33). The atmosphere can better be destabilized. It may explain why with local afforestation precipitations are stronger than for large scale afforestations.

Run off - In spring, the run off is significantly stronger with local afforestation than with large scale afforestations. It is because the run off response to climate change increases significantly more with the local afforestation than with large scale afforestations.(figure 29(b)) It is a consequence of the stronger precipitations with local afforestation than with large scale afforestations (figure 29(b)).

Key message - The Gers variable responses depend on the afforestation scale because they depend on the dynamic (horizontal wind and vertical wind), which change with a local or a large scale afforestation.

As a consequence, experimental afforestation protocols with large scale afforestations, or with models which can't simulate dynamic answers to afforestation, have to be checked on and controled. It is possible that they can't answer to questions of helping local adaptation strategies with afforestation.

Figure 33: Sensible heat flux. Same as Figure 17.

4 Discussion

4.1 Representativeness and robustness of the results obtained

In this study, we try to compare the effects of global climate change and the effects of local-to-regional afforestation on the climate of the Gers department. However, the results described in this study are obtained with a single regional climate model (CNRM-ALADIN64), itself coupled to only one surface scheme (SURFEX-CTRIIP), and driven by only one GCM simulation (CNRM-ESM2-1 r1i1p1f2) under a given scenario (SSP3-7.0) and for a given Global Warming Level (+2°C). We can therefore question the robustness of the results obtained and wonder how they could be modified by changing any element of this complex modelling chain. In particular, it has been proven that climate response to afforestation is strongly model dependent and that even the sign of the response can change from one model to another even if they follow the same afforestation protocol ([7]). We therefore consider that it would be important to do numerical experiments with the same protocol in a multi-model framework in order to assess the robustness of these results.

In addition, we have decided to work on the Gers department but we are fully aware that other choices of the studied area may have lead to different results in particular depending on the latitude of the chosen area, the presence of snow cover in Spring or the simulated climate change without afforestation. So it is likely that our results can not be simply generalized to any other small geographical area in Europe.

On a longer term, both points question the feasibility of performing robust assessments of local afforestation adaptation plans. Indeed, developing multi-model experiments for every targeted areas in the world may simply be not affordable by the scientific community.

4.2 Modelling platform limitations

In this study, we use the SURFEX land surface model to represent the land surface processus and the coupling with the atmosphere. However SURFEX representation of the surface isn't perfect. For instance, the crops aren't irrigated in our experiences, while there are often irrigated in real life in the Gers. Replacing irrigated crops by forests, or non-irrigated crops by forests, could give

different results. Indeed, irrigated soils evaporate more than non irrigated soils. Smaller evaporation differences between the afforested soils and the reference soils could be observed in the results. Then, the values of the 12 vegetation patches in ISBA for the tile Nature are taken from the data base Ecoclimap ([12]), with a version of 2010, which is relatively old, and may not represent perfectly the vegetation distribution at the surface today. The surface model used could be better to trust the results of the study and attack local adaptation strategies questions.

Besides, ALADIN has its own biases, for example for the representation of the diurnal cycle of precipitation or nebulosity. That may affect our results on the nebulosity, on precipitations, on the surface radiation exchanges, and on evaporation. The existence of those biases pushes for the use of a multi-model approach in which the biases can be different from one model to another. It also pushes to test such afforestation experiment with convection-permitting regional climate models at kilometer-scale which have a clear added-value on the standard RCMs for the diurnal cycle representation.

4.3 Validation of the study hypothesis

The study does reason analysis to explain the results of the afforestation experiences. To confirm those explanations, which are often hypothesis, sensibility analysis should be done for each process to explain each phenomena. For now, it is difficult to attribute clearly a physical process to an answer in hydrological cycle for instance without those analysis.

4.4 The afforestation protocol

This study is idealized and would need to evolve closer to a realistic experiment before thinking of sharing results with policymakers. Indeed, 100% of trees is added in one grid cell when it's not rock or bare soil, which is not realistic in the Gers department.

The afforestation in the model is also really brutal, as we add an adult tree directly. There is no growth period of the tree, although a spin up is used to try to lead the soil to an equilibrium after the choc.

Then, to explain better the spatial structure of some variable answers to afforestation, linked on the specie of tree present, it would be interesting to make afforestation of the Gers simulations with only boradleaves and only evergreens. For the moment, the effects of both species can be mixed and difficult to interpret, as we can have both trees on one grid cell, with one answer in atmospheric variable.

5 Conclusion

The goal of the study is to compare the effect of climate change to the effects of regional afforestation. It explores the effects of the Gers afforestation on the Gers climatic variables answers to climate change. It assess if the climatic variables of the Gers react differently in response to the local afforestation of the Gers, or to large scale afforestations.

To do so a reference simulation is run in a past climate (1986-2005), and another in a future

climate (2043-2062). The difference between both gives the climate change effects on the Gers climatic variables. Afforestations simulations are run in the future climate, with afforestation of the Gers department in France, of France, and of EURO-CORDEX domain. The difference between each afforestation simulation, and the reference simulation, gives different afforestation scales effects on the Gers climatic variables.

It gives an impression on how the land and the atmosphere could react to the Gers idealized afforestation.

A first result is that afforesting a very local area can have strong effects, compared to climate change effect alone. Local effects of climate change is comparable to local afforestation effects. For instance in spring, climate change induced warming on the Gers is $+0.9^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the local Gers afforestation induced warming is $+0.7^{\circ}\text{C}$ more. The Gers temperature answer to climate change with the Gers afforestation is then $+1.6^{\circ}\text{C}$ (34).

Then, afforestation effects on climatic variables go through various processes which can be in competition between each other. The dominant process and effect depend on the season, the region and on the specie of tree. It is a complex problematic, where general conclusions are hard to make. In winter, the near surface air temperature, precipitations, runoff and soil moisture increase in response to climate change with the Gers afforestation. In spring, the near surface air temperature, the runoff and the water on the ground increase in response to climate change with Gers afforestation. In summer, there is a spatial correlation between the evergreens and the warming of the near surface air temperature, and the broadleaves and the cooling of the temperature extremes in response to climate change with Gers afforestation.

A surprising result from this study is the order of magnitude of energy and hydrological phenomena on the Gers in response to different afforestation scales. No matter the afforestation scale, which goes from the continent to the department, the answers inside the Gers have similar magnitudes.

Then, a valuable insight from this study is the key role of the dynamic in response to a very local afforestation experiment. Indeed, not only one dimensional and local effects are observed in answer to afforestation. As a consequence, some variables have opposite answers to climate change depending on if the afforestation is local or large scaled. Those differences are mainly due to the dynamic ; ascendencies in winter, and differences in horizontal wind speeds in winter, spring and summer. It highlights that dynamics can change the reaction of an area to afforestation.

Dynamics is dependant on the size of the forest, and have a key role on local climatic variables responses. It means that Europe wide afforestation studies cannot be used to assess questions of local afforestation adaptation strategies. It could have been the case if only local effects would dominate. This result could help as a guidance on how to tackle adaptation strategies policies assessment with afforestation. Indeed afforestation studies as LUCAS (Land Use Accross Scales) for instance can have high resolution, sometime 50km, and they afforest all a continent, as Europe ([7],[4],[1]). Which such configuration, local aspects as dynamic enhanced by a very constrained afforestation can't be seen, while they have strong impacts. Research on local adaptation strategy evaluations is needed.

A perspective of the study is to change some methodology choices of the paper. Another department or location could be studied, as the Gers is influenced by the nearby west French coast and Atlantic ocean.

A next step would be trying new experiments with doubling the forest density, to see if responses of the Gers climatic variables to a lower forest density addition are still significant.

Another perspective is to study different crescent steps of afforestation, to assess the linearity of different variable answers to an increasing afforestation.

Then, the impacts of several weather regimes on afforestation effects could be studied. Precipitation are a lot influenced by dynamics on the Gers, especially in winter, so different responses to afforestation may appear with different weather regimes.

Furthermore, the impact of dry years and wet years on the hydrological cycle in response to afforestation were studied, and an effect was observed. It could be the gist of a new paper, to pursue this one, looking at the impact of the year dryness on afforestation effects too.

Finally, this study encourages going to fine resolution, for instance to study forest breezes. Indeed 12 km is too high a resolution for such a local phenomenon, while afforestation impact on wind can be a key process in the atmospheric answer to afforestation.

The poor representation of anthropisation on land can lack the quality of the model results. A finer resolution, plus anthropisation modelisation, would benefit studies on local adaptation strategy evaluations.

6 Annexe

	tas (°C)	pr (mm/jour)	tran (mm/jour)	hfls (W m-2)	mrro (mm/jour)	clt (%)	10m wind (m/s)	hfss (W.m-2)
DJF								
ssp_reference - his_reference	0.875189	-0.301357	0.084032	1.824461	-0.285005	-0.064259	-0.285445	1.184321
ssp_gerforest - ssp_reference	0.540807	0.112376	-0.091108	-2.480698	0.043265	0.143448	-0.518777	2.319294
ssp_fraforest - ssp_reference	0.606090	0.041506	-0.101005	-3.472313	-0.013313	-0.102306	-0.659048	3.372749
ssp_eurforest - ssp_reference	0.647650	0.031150	-0.106064	-3.811987	-0.047265	-0.367332	-0.665029	3.425733
MAM								
ssp_reference - his_reference	0.872374	-0.244467	0.152274	2.012329	-0.214781	-5.505203	-0.022252	2.192579
ssp_gerforest - ssp_reference	0.683605	0.026602	-0.501933	-9.730728	0.086620	0.030952	-0.462249	14.144482
ssp_fraforest - ssp_reference	0.986263	-0.074286	-0.499607	-11.180485	0.052826	-0.636147	-0.543607	14.756516
ssp_eurforest - ssp_reference	1.318442	-0.255811	-0.480294	-12.048950	-0.017953	-1.723392	-0.564312	15.790260
JJA								
ssp_reference - his_reference	1.691450	-0.248518	-0.246509	-10.080151	-0.037063	-3.826378	-0.226979	11.093788
ssp_gerforest - ssp_reference	0.211506	0.113585	0.385255	14.809887	0.028000	-0.810284	-0.598475	0.559875
ssp_fraforest - ssp_reference	0.561407	-0.076985	0.272424	9.228527	0.001178	-1.292946	-0.659860	5.785675
ssp_eurforest - ssp_reference	0.751603	-0.056910	0.246240	8.268154	0.005719	-0.659687	-0.652508	6.638634
SON								
ssp_reference - his_reference	1.547442	-0.002980	0.006357	-1.035717	-0.016319	-5.044209	-0.058596	1.742723
ssp_gerforest - ssp_reference	0.498921	0.012671	-0.060396	-0.637428	0.012706	-0.109100	-0.530571	4.592539
ssp_fraforest - ssp_reference	0.751603	-0.213670	-0.111807	-3.786716	-0.010092	-0.054840	-0.656835	7.123871
ssp_eurforest - ssp_reference	1.017859	-0.277081	-0.139975	-5.486082	-0.032450	-1.487469	-0.672469	8.040203
ANNUEL								
ssp_reference - his_reference	1.246614	-0.199331	-0.000961	-1.819767	-0.138292	-3.610008	-0.034829	4.053350
ssp_gerforest - ssp_reference	0.483710	0.066308	-0.067046	0.490253	0.042648	-0.186245	-0.527518	5.404049
ssp_fraforest - ssp_reference	0.726341	-0.080859	-0.109999	-2.302750	0.007650	-0.521561	-0.629838	7.759705
ssp_eurforest - ssp_reference	0.941657	-0.139663	-0.120023	-3.269718	-0.022987	-1.059467	-0.638580	8.473709

Figure 34: On the columns, the variables looked. On the lines, the anomaly of these variables with climate change and with the several afforestation experiments. Line ssp_reference - his_reference : anomaly of the variable in response to climate change between the periods 1986-2005 and 2043-2062. Line ssp_gerforest - ssp_reference : anomaly of the variable in response to the Gers afforestation in the period 2043-2062. Line ssp_fraforest - ssp_reference : anomaly of the variable in response to France afforestation in the period 2043-2062. Line ssp_eurforest - ssp_reference : anomaly of the variable in response to EURO-CORDEX domain afforestation in the period 2043-2062.

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